

1 **Farm dust exposure reduces cytokine- and rhinovirus-induced IL-33 expression in**
2 **bronchial epithelial cells**

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31

32 **Abstract**

33

34 Multiple studies have indicated that growing up on a traditional farm is associated with protection
35 against wheezing, allergies, and asthma. Experimental studies showed that this is mediated in part by
36 exposure to farm dust from cow sheds, likely involving an effect on airway epithelial functioning.
37 Environmental triggers such as allergens, pollutants and pathogens can damage the airway epithelial
38 barrier which is accompanied by the release of epithelial alarmin cytokines such as IL-33, IL-25 and
39 TSLP, that activate an array of innate immune cells. Upon activation, these cells trigger T helper (Th)2
40 inflammatory responses, which contribute to both the development and the progression of asthma.
41 The aim of the present study is to investigate if farm dust extract (FD) affects the expression of the
42 alarmin IL-33 in cultured primary bronchial epithelial cells (PBEC) and to investigate the underlying
43 mechanism. To this end, PBEC were infected with rhinovirus (RV) or stimulated with the
44 proinflammatory cytokines TNF- α /IFN- γ to increase IL-33 mRNA in presence or absence of FD. We
45 found that FD reduced RV- and TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced mRNA expression of IL-33. We next determined
46 the effects of FD on TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced IL-33 protein expression and found this was also reduced by
47 FD. Analysis of the signaling mechanisms underlying the protective effects of FD on IL-33 expression
48 showed that FD partly reduced IFN- γ -induced phosphorylation of STAT1, suggesting that the IFN- γ
49 receptor (IFNGR)-Janus kinase (JAK)-signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT)-1 pathway
50 may be involved. These results indicate that FD inhibits RV- and TNF- α /IFN- γ -mediated induction of
51 IL-33 in cultures of PBEC. Future studies are needed to exploit these findings for novel treatments of
52 asthma directed towards the reduction of IL-33-mediated Th2 inflammation in the airways.

53

63 Introduction

64

65 Pre-school wheeze, genetic susceptibility, allergic sensitization, and microbiome composition of the
66 gut and airways are amongst the major risk factors for early onset asthma¹⁻⁴. Pre-school wheezing can
67 be triggered by several respiratory viruses, of which rhinovirus (RV) infections form the most
68 important risk factor⁵. Furthermore, impairment of the airway epithelial barrier (resulting from
69 genetic polymorphisms and/or environmental insults before birth and in early life) will increase the
70 susceptibility towards (viral) infections, allergens and other insults and this may eventually increase
71 airway epithelial damage, inflammation and aberrant repair⁶.

72 In the airways of asthmatic children, both expression and release of the alarmin IL-33 are elevated
73 compared to healthy controls⁷. IL-33 is involved early in the development of T helper (Th)2 immunity
74 and is a central mediator in both Th2 cell and Th2 innate lymphoid cell (ILC2)-driven responses to RV,
75 causing aberrant airway remodeling and asthma^{5,6,8-10}. In the airways, IL-33 is stored in the nucleus
76 and is released upon cellular damage, caused by cigarette smoke-/pollutant exposure or by viral- or
77 bacterial infections, but also certain allergens or proteases (papain) can trigger the release of IL-33^{11,12}.

78 Although IL-33 is constitutively expressed, expression of IL-33 can be increased as a response to
79 proinflammatory stimuli such as TNF- α and IFN- γ and after RV infections in airway epithelial cells^{8,13}.

80 Several Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) studies have identified polymorphisms in both *IL33*
81 and *IL1RL1* (suppression of tumorigenicity 2 [ST2]) genes that are associated with pre-school wheezing
82 and/or asthma development¹⁴⁻¹⁹. Furthermore, recent clinical trials using IL-33-blocking antibodies
83 showed efficacy in asthma patients and in former smokers with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
84 (COPD)^{20,21}. This indicates that IL-33 plays not only a critical role in asthma development, but also later
85 in life in those that have developed asthma and COPD. Similar to IL-33, levels of IL-25 and thymic
86 stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) are increased in asthma patients and further enhanced by exposure to
87 allergens, RV or by inflammatory cytokines, thereby enhancing type 2 inflammation^{5,6,9,22,23}.

88 Children that grow up on a traditional farm develop less wheezing, allergies and asthma, suggesting a
89 protective effect of this environment^{24,25}. This has been attributed to both exposure to dust from
90 especially cow stables, as well as consumption of (raw) cow milk²⁶. Experimental studies in mice
91 showed that repetitive treatment with lipopolysaccharide (LPS; a component of farm dust²⁷) or farm
92 dust extract (FD) protected against the development of house dust mite (HDM)–induced allergic
93 airway inflammation and reduced HDM-induced IL-33 expression in murine lung epithelial cells²⁸.
94 Furthermore, it was shown in cultured human primary bronchial epithelial cells (PBEC) that epithelial
95 barrier function and RV clearance were both enhanced upon treatment with FD²⁹. Both studies
96 demonstrated that treatment with either toll-like receptor (TLR)2 and/or TLR4 agonists could mimic
97 the observed effects of farm dust^{28,29}. However, the effect of FD on the epithelial alarmins such as IL-
98 33 in human airway epithelial cells was never investigated.

99 The aim of the present study was to determine whether and how FD exposure affects the expression
100 of the epithelial alarmin IL-33 in primary bronchial epithelial cells. To this end, both submerged
101 undifferentiated cultures and fully differentiated cultures of PBEC were exposed to TNF- α and IFN- γ
102 or infected with RV to increase the expression of IL-33, and the effect of simultaneous exposure to
103 and/or pretreatment with FD was assessed. We furthermore analyzed effects of FD on cellular
104 pathways regulating IFN- γ -mediated IL-33 expression.

105 **Materials and Methods**

106

107 **Primary bronchial epithelial cell (PBEC) culture**

108 PBEC were isolated from macroscopically normal lung tissue obtained from patients undergoing
109 resection surgery for lung cancer at the Leiden University Medical Center, the Netherlands. Patients
110 from which this lung tissue was derived were enrolled in the biobank *via* a no-objection system for
111 coded anonymous further use of such tissue (www.coreon.org). However, since 01-09-2022, patients
112 are enrolled in the biobank using active informed consent in accordance with local regulations from
113 the LUMC biobank with approval by the institutional medical ethical committee (B20.042/Ab/ab and
114 B20.042/Kb/kb). Cells were cultured as previously described³⁰. Briefly, cultures of bronchial epithelial
115 cells (passage 1) were first expanded in T75 culture flasks that were pre-coated with a mixture of 30
116 µg/mL Purecol (Advanced BioMatrix, San Diego, CA, USA), 5 µg/mL human fibronectin (Promocell,
117 Heidelberg, Germany) and 10 µg/mL BSA (Fraction V; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bleiswijk, The
118 Netherlands). Next, cells (passage 2) from a single donor or a donor mix (mix of 4-5 different donors)
119 were seeded at a density of 3000 cells per cm² for submerged cultures of (S)-PBEC on pre-coated 12-
120 well or 24-well plates (Corning Costar, Cambridge, MA, USA). Pre-coated semi-permeable Transwell
121 inserts (12 mm, 0.4 µm pore-size, Corning Costar) were seeded with 40,000 cells per insert for seeding
122 of single donors or with 150,000 cells per insert for seeding a donor mix of 4 to 5 donors (30,000-
123 40,000 cells/donor). For the donor mixes, the higher seeding density compared to individual cultures
124 resulted in near-confluency to avoid selective advantage of possible faster-proliferating cells of the
125 selected donors. The cells were cultured in a 1:1 mixture of BEpiCM-b-medium (1:1) (ScienCell
126 Research Laboratories, Sanbio, Uden, The Netherlands) and DMEM medium (STEMCELL technologies,
127 Köln, Germany respectively). This so-called BD medium was supplemented with Bronchial Epithelial
128 Cell Growth Supplement (ScienCell Research Laboratories) and additional 1 nM EC-23 (Bio-Techne,
129 Dublin, Ireland) (for the submerged phase of PBEC cultures on inserts only), 25 mM HEPES (Thermo
130 Fisher Scientific, Bleiswijk, The Netherlands), 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin
131 (Sanbio), and used for culture of the cells at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. After the cells growing on inserts had

132 reached confluence (after 5-7 days), apical medium was removed, and the cells were cultured at the
133 air-liquid interface (ALI) and medium was changed 3 times a week with complete (c)BD-medium
134 supplemented with Bronchial Epithelial Cell Growth Supplement and additional 50 nM EC-23. Before
135 every medium change, the apical surface of these ALI-PBEC cultures was washed with PBS to remove
136 mucus and cellular debris. After 14 days of air-exposed culture, the cells produced mucus and had
137 developed cilia, and cultures were used for experiments. S-PBEC were cultured until they reached 70-
138 90% confluence after 4-5 days and next cultured for 24 h in cBD-medium without the addition of
139 growth factors (BPE, EGF) and hydrocortisone before stimulation (= BD-starvation medium).

140

141 **Experimental design**

142 Submerged (S) undifferentiated and differentiated air-liquid interface (ALI) cultures of PBEC were pre-
143 treated with FD (200 µg/mL for S-PBEC; 400 µg/mL in the basal medium for ALI-PBEC) for 24 h. Optimal
144 FD concentrations were determined using dose-response experiments in both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC.
145 Cells were stimulated with 20 ng/mL TNF-α (PeproTech, London, UK) and 30 ng/mL INF-γ (PeproTech),
146 or with 100 ng/mL IL-4 (PeproTech) and 10 µg/mL poly(I:C) (Invivogen, Toulouse, France) in presence
147 or absence of FD for 6 h and 24 h to assess changes in gene expression and to measure release of IL-8
148 and CXCL-10, or for 8 h to assess protein levels (for IL-33 protein expression by using HEK-Blue™ IL-33
149 reporter cells (Invivogen) and immunofluorescence staining (Figure 1A)^{13,22,23}. To elucidate the
150 mechanism underlying the inhibition of IFN-γ-mediated IL-33 by FD, S-PBEC were pretreated with
151 inhibitors of downstream IFN-γ signaling pathways (2x10⁻⁶ M Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitor I
152 [Calbiochem/Merck Life Science NV, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; JAK- signal transducer and
153 activator of transcription (STAT) signaling], 4x10⁻⁵ M SB203580 [Bio-Connect, Huissen, The
154 Netherlands; p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling], 1x10⁻⁶ M AG1478 [Bio-Connect;
155 epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) signaling] and 1x10⁻⁶ M BAY-11 [Tocris, Bio-technie Ltd,
156 Abington, UK; nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF-κB) signaling]) or 200

157 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ FD for 1 h and stimulated with 30 ng/mL IFN- γ alone for 6 h to assess *IL33* mRNA expression
158 and release of LDH, and for 30 minutes for western blot analysis of phosphorylated (p-)STAT1, p-p38,
159 p-EGFR and GAPDH.

160

161 **Rhinovirus Infection**

162 S-PBEC that were cultured on 24-well plates, were incubated for 24 h in BD starvation medium in
163 presence or in absence of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ FD before infection with RV-A1B at a multiplicity of infection
164 (MOI) of 0.5 (Figure 1A) in 150 μL BD-starvation medium with gentle room temperature shaking.
165 Optimal RV-dose and strain was selected in a pilot experiment in which S-PBEC were infected with
166 different MOI of both RV-A16 and RV-A1B (Figure S1). After 2 h, the non-bound RV was removed by
167 washing the cells three times with Opti-MEM (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and fresh BD-starvation
168 medium was added. Cultures were harvested at 48 h post infection (hpi) by collection of medium and
169 lysis of cells for isolation of RNA (Figure 1A).

170

171 **Farm dust collection and extraction**

172 FD was collected in 2018 from traditional Bavarian cow farms in a rural area around Munich. The dust
173 was collected from shelves at least one meter above ground and prepared as previously described
174 with some slight modifications²⁹. After dialysis using a Spectra/Por cellulose ester dialysis membrane
175 (MWCO 3,500 Da, Breda, The Netherlands), it was filtered using a 0.22 μm polyethersulfone
176 membrane and directly collected. The resulting sterile extract was filled into a 5 mL glass vial at a
177 volume of 3.0 mL and freeze-dried. The lyophilized extract was then divided into 5 mg portions and
178 stored at -80°C in 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes. Prior to each experiment, the FD extract was
179 dissolved in cBD medium.

180

181 **Preparation of rhinovirus stocks**

182 Rhinovirus type A-016 (RV-A16, major group, ATCC VR-283) and Rhinovirus type A-01B (RV-A1B, minor
183 group, ATCC VR-1645™) viral stocks were prepared in H1-HeLa cells (ATCC CRL-1958™) as described
184 previously³¹.

185

186 **HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells**

187 HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells (Invivogen, Toulouse, France) were refreshed twice a week with DMEM
188 (STEMCELL technologies), P/S (Sanbio), Glutamax (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 10% FCS (v/v) with
189 addition of HEK-Blue™ selection antibiotics and normocin (Invivogen) (HEK-Blue™ medium) according
190 to the manufacturer 's instructions and maintained at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.

191

192 **HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cell assay**

193 Cellular IL-33 protein levels were measured using HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells according to the
194 manufacturer's instruction (Invivogen) with some minor adaptations. In short, after 8 h of stimulation,
195 the medium of the stimulated S-PBEC or ALI-PBEC was replaced by HEK-Blue™ medium without
196 selection antibiotics and normocin (HEK-Blue™ assay medium) and frozen at -80 °C. Cells were next
197 disrupted by applying 3 freeze-thaw cycles and incubated in presence of 100,000 HEK-Blue™ IL-33
198 reporter cells in a 96-well plate (Corning Costar) for 24 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter
199 cells have been transfected with IL-1RL1 (ST2) and contain an NF-κB/AP-1 inducible SEAP (secreted
200 embryonic alkaline phosphatase) reporter gene, which is transcribed upon activation of IL-1RL1
201 (ST2)/IL-1RAcP by IL-33. SEAP levels in the HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cell supernatant was measured
202 using a spectrophotometer at O.D. 650 nm (Figure 1A).

203

204 **RNA isolation, reverse transcription (RT) and quantitative (q)PCR**

205 To extract RNA, cells were lysed in RNA lysis buffer (Promega Benelux B.V., Leiden, The Netherlands).
 206 The Maxwell RSC tissue RNA extraction kit (Promega) was utilized for robotic extraction of the total
 207 RNA, which was quantified using the Nanodrop ND-1000 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Nanodrop
 208 Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA). To synthesize cDNA, 1 µg of total RNA was reverse transcribed
 209 using oligo dT primers (Qiagen Benelux B.V. in Venlo, The Netherlands) and M-MLV Polymerase
 210 (Promega Benelux B.V) at a temperature of 42 °C. The qPCR reactions were performed in triplicate on
 211 a CFX-384 Real-Time PCR detection system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Veenendaal, The Netherlands),
 212 using the primers specified in table I and IQ SYBRGreen supermix (Bio-Rad Laboratories). The CFX-
 213 manager software (Bio-Rad Laboratories) was used to calculate arbitrary gene expression through the
 214 relative standard curve method. Two reference genes that were selected using the "Genorm method"
 215 (Primer design, Southampton, UK), were used to calculate normalized gene expression.

216

Gene	Encoding Protein	Sequence forward primer	Sequence reverse primer	GenBank accession #
<i>YWHAZ*</i>	Tyrosine 3-monooxygenase/tryptophan 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta	ACTTTTGGTACATTGTGGCTCA A	CGCCAGGACAAACCAGTAT	NM_00113 5699.1
<i>RPL27*</i>	Ribosomal protein L27	ATCGCCAAGAGATCAAAGATAA	TCTGAAGACATCCTTATTGACG	NM_00098 8
<i>RV-A1B</i>	Rhinovirus A1B	CCATCGCTCACTATTTCAGCAC	TCTATCCCGAACACACTGTCC	D00239.1
<i>RV-A16</i>	Rhinovirus-A16	ACCCTCAATACATACGCCAACT	TTCCAAGCCATCCATTCCA	L24917.1
<i>IL33</i>	Interleukin 33	ACTCACTGTACATTGGGCA	GCATCCAGAGGTCAGGTGAT	NM_03343 9
<i>TSLP</i>	Thymic stromal lymphopoietin	ATGTTTCGCCATGAAAATAAGGC	GCGACGCCACAATCCTTGTA	NM_03303 5.5
<i>CXCL8</i>	C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 8	CTGGACCCCAAGGAAAAC	TGGCAACCCTACAACAGAC	NM_00058 4
<i>CXCL10</i>	C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 10	GTGGCATTCAAGGAGTACCTC	TGATGGCCTTCGATTCTGGATT	NM_00156 5
<i>IRF1</i>	Interferon regulatory factor 1	ACCCTGGCTAGAGATGCAGA	TGCTTTGTATCGGCTGTGT	NM_00219 8.3
<i>ICAM1</i>	Intercellular adhesion molecule 1	ATGCCAGACATCTGTGTCC	GGGGTCTCTATGCCAACAA	NM_00020 1

217 Table I. PCR primers and sequences used for quantitative PCR

218 *Used as a reference gene, selected using the Genorm method

219 **Western blot**

220 Cells were lysed in ice-cold RIPA buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), containing phosphatase and
221 protease inhibitors (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and stored at -80 °C until further use. RIPA lysates were
222 centrifuged at 10,000 × g for 15 min at 4 °C and dissolved in reducing LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher
223 Scientific), heated for 5 min at 100° C and applied on a pre-cast 4-15% SDS-PAGE gel (Bio-Rad
224 Laboratories). Next, proteins were blotted using Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer Pack mini system (Bio-Rad
225 Laboratories) and non-specific binding sites were blocked in Tris-buffered saline (TBS) containing
226 0.01% Tween 20 (v/v) and 5% (w/v) skimmed milk for detection of phosphorylated (p-)STAT1, p-EGFR,
227 p-p38, and GAPDH. Membranes were probed with primary antibodies specific for p-STAT1, p-EGFR, p-
228 p38, and GAPDH in blocking buffer (Table II). Next, the membranes were incubated in 1/2,500 diluted
229 goat-anti-mouse-HRP for p-p38 or in 1/2,500 diluted goat-anti-rabbit-HRP (Cell Signaling Technology,
230 Leiden, The Netherlands) for p-STAT1, p-EGFR and GAPDH in TBS containing 0.01% Tween 20 (v/v)
231 (Table II). SuperSignal West Pico ECL Substrate (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used to visualize the
232 protein bands using The ChemiDoc™ Touch imager in combination with Image Lab™ software (Bio-
233 Rad Laboratories).

234

235 **Immunofluorescence staining**

236 Cells grown on precoated 6 mm coverslips (S-PBEC) or on Transwell inserts (ALI-PBEC) were fixed in
237 4% paraformaldehyde (Merck Life Science NV) in PBS for 10 min on ice and washed with ice-cold PBS.
238 Next, cells were permeabilized with methanol for 10 min at 4 °C, washed in PBS and blocked with
239 PBS/1% (w/v) BSA/0.3% (v/v) Triton-X-100 (PBT) for 30 min at 4 °C. Next, cells were treated for 30 min
240 with SFX-signal enhancer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) followed by incubation with primary antibodies in
241 PBT for 1 h at RT (Table II). After washing in PBS, cells were incubated with Alexa Fluor labeled
242 secondary antibodies together with DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole, Sigma Aldrich) in PBT for 30
243 min at RT in the dark (Table II). Finally, cells were mounted in ProLong™ Gold Antifade Mountant

244 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and images were acquired using a TCS SP5 Confocal Laser Scanning
 245 Microscope (Leica Microsystems B.V., Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and LAS AF Lite software (Leica
 246 Microsystems B.V.). The images were further analyzed using maximum intensity view. To quantify the
 247 number of IL-33⁺ cells, IL-33⁺ and DAPI⁺ nuclei were counted per 62.500 μm² field. Per donor, three
 248 fields were analyzed (containing 200-500 cells on average). The threshold was set based on the control
 249 condition and kept constant throughout the quantification of each staining.

250 **TABLE II**

Antibody	Supplier	Catalog #	species	Antibody dilution
<i>SDS-PAGE western blot:</i>				
p-STAT-1	CST	9167	rabbit	1/1000
p-EGFR	CST	2234	rabbit	1/500
p-p38	CST	9216	mouse	1/500
GAPDH	CST	2118	rabbit	1/2000
<i>Immunofluorescence staining:</i>				
HRP-linked anti-mouse IgG	CST	7076	goat	1/2000
HRP-linked anti-rabbit IgG	CST	7074	goat	1/2000
TP63	Abcam	ab52635	rabbit	1/100
Foxj1	R&D Systems	AF3619	goat	1/200
Mucin 5AC	CST	61193T	rabbit	1/400
Mucin 5B	Santa Cruz	sc-20119	rabbit	1/100
Alexa Fluor 488 anti-mouse IgG (H+L)	TFS	A11001	goat	1/200
Alexa Fluor 568 anti-rabbit IgG (H+L)	TFS	A10042	donkey	1/200
Alexa Fluor 647 anti-goat IgG (H+L)	TFS	A21447	donkey	1/200

251 Table II. Primary and secondary antibodies used for SDS-PAGE western blot and immunofluorescence
 252 staining; (CST: Cell Signaling Technology, Leiden, The Netherlands; Abcam, Cambridge, UK; R&D
 253 Systems, Bio-technie Ltd, Abington, UK; Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Heidelberg, Germany; TFS:
 254 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bleiswijk, The Netherlands)

255

256

257 **ELISA**

258 CXCL8/IL-8 and CXCL-10 production by S-PBEC was determined using the CXCL8/IL-8 Duoset kit (Bio-
 259 Techne) and BD OptEIA™ Set Human IP-10 (BD Biosciences, Vianen, The Netherlands), respectively,
 260 according to the manufacturer's protocol.

261

262 **LDH assay**

263

264 S-PBEC were pretreated with inhibitors of downstream IFN- γ signaling pathways (JAK inhibitor I,
265 SB203580, AG1478 and BAY-11) or FD for 1 h and stimulated with IFN- γ alone for 6 h, and LDH release
266 was assessed using a Promega Cytotoxicity Detection Kit (Promega) according to manufactures'
267 protocol.

268

269

270 **Statistical analysis**

271 Statistical analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA).
272 To analyze qPCR results, fold change in gene expression of the stimuli compared to control (CNTRL)
273 was calculated. All data were analyzed using a Student's t-test or by using a two-way ANOVA and the
274 Šídák or Dunnett's post-hoc test. Differences at p values < 0.05 were considered statistically
275 significant.

276

277 **Results**

278

279 **Farm dust extract decreases rhinovirus- and TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced IL-33 production in PBEC**

280 First, we investigated whether FD exposure could modulate mRNA expression of IL-33. Several studies
281 in PBEC have shown that IL-33 mRNA expression was increased by RV infections or by exposure to the
282 proinflammatory cytokine mix TNF- α /IFN- γ ^{8,13}. S-PBEC were pretreated with or without FD for 24 h
283 and the cells were subsequently infected in absence of FD with RV-A1B (Figure 1A). We observed that
284 FD pretreatment inhibited RV-mediated increase of *IL33* mRNA, without affecting vRNA levels (Figure
285 1B-C). We next investigated if FD inhibits expression of IL-33 in both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC after TNF-
286 α /IFN- γ -stimulation and demonstrated that FD impaired the induction of *IL33* mRNA and protein by

287 TNF- α /IFN- γ in both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC (Figure 1D-G). In addition, immunofluorescence staining of
288 IL-33 in both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC showed localization of IL-33 in the nucleus, (which is in line with
289 previous reports³²) and an increase in the number of IL-33⁺ cells after TNF- α /IFN- γ stimulation (Figure
290 1H-I). FD treatment clearly reduced the TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced number of IL-33⁺ cells in S-PBEC, whereas
291 the effect of both TNF- α /IFN- γ stimulation and FD treatment on IL-33 was less prominent in ALI-PBEC
292 (Figure 1H-I). We next investigated whether active release of IL-33 was also inhibited by FD-treatment
293 and used papain (Merck Life Science NV) to activate IL-33 release¹² into the supernatant of S-PBEC and
294 HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells were used for detection of IL-33 release. We observed that TNF- α /IFN-
295 γ stimulation caused a limited release of IL-33, which was inhibited by FD but not further enhanced by
296 addition of papain. Increasing papain concentrations to a level that would induce a substantial and
297 significant release of IL-33 was not possible due to the toxic effects of papain-containing conditioned
298 medium from stimulated S-PBEC on HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells (Figure S2). Altogether, this
299 indicated that FD actively represses induction of *IL33* mRNA expression both after TNF- α /IFN- γ
300 stimulation and after RV infection with a more prominent effect in S-PBEC.

301

302 **IL-33 is mainly expressed by basal cells in differentiated PBEC**

303 FD treatment showed the strongest inhibitory effect in S-PBEC, cells that are grown submerged in a
304 monolayer and solely consist of basal epithelial cells³³. To investigate differences in localization of IL-
305 33 in the bronchial epithelial cell layer between S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC, we used 8 h TNF- α /IFN- γ -
306 stimulated S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC to maximize the number of IL-33-positive cells. Immunofluorescence
307 staining followed by confocal analysis was performed with antibodies directed against IL-33 in
308 combination with antibodies directed against the main epithelial cell types: basal- (TP63), ciliated-
309 (Foxj1) and secretory cells (MUC5AC and MUC5B). In both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC, IL-33 was co-localized
310 with TP63 (Figure 2A). IL-33 was mainly localized at the basal side of the cell layer where the basal
311 cells reside and showed no colocalization with markers for both ciliated- and secretory cells (Figure

312 2B). In conclusion, these observations show that IL-33 was mainly expressed by basal cells of both S-
313 PBEC and ALI-PBEC.

314

315 **Farm dust extract interferes with IFN- γ -IFNGR-JAK-STAT1 signaling in IFN- γ -stimulated PBEC**

316 We next aimed to determine the mechanism underlying the reduction of TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced IL-33
317 by FD. We first compared the effects of IFN- γ alone to IFN- γ together with TNF- α on IL-33 protein and
318 mRNA and demonstrated that IFN- γ was the main driver of TNF- α /IFN- γ -mediated IL-33 expression
319 (Figure S3), in line with findings from others³⁴⁻³⁶. Therefore, we used IFN- γ -stimulated S-PBEC as a
320 model to determine the mechanisms underlying the inhibitory effects of FD on IL-33. First, we
321 investigated possible pathways downstream of IFN- γ -signaling that might result in activation of *IL33*
322 mRNA expression. According to studies in epithelial cells, activation of JAK- STAT1-, EGFR-, p38 MAPK-
323 and/or NF- κ B signaling have been implicated in IFN- γ -mediated induction of *IL33* mRNA^{34,36,37}. We
324 therefore pretreated the cells with inhibitors of downstream-IFN- γ signaling pathways (JAK, p38
325 MAPK, EGFR and NF- κ B) or FD before stimulation with IFN- γ . The results showed that, in addition to
326 FD, also inhibition of JAK-STAT, P38 MAPK and EGFR decreased expression of *IL33* in S-PBEC (Figure
327 3A). We next assessed if FD was able to reduce activation of either STAT1, EGFR or p38 by pretreating
328 the cells with FD and with inhibitors of downstream IFN- γ signaling pathways as controls followed by
329 stimulation with IFN- γ . LL-37 was included as a positive control for activation of the above-mentioned
330 pathways³⁸. We measured LDH release to monitor possible toxicity of the used inhibitors and found
331 no major effects (Figure S4A). Western blot analysis of phosphorylated (p)-STAT1, EGFR and p38
332 showed that preincubation with FD partly inhibited p-STAT1 (trend towards significance) in IFN- γ -
333 stimulated S-PBEC (Figure 3B). Furthermore, FD did not affect levels of p-EGFR or p-p38 (Figure S4B).
334 We next investigated if the inhibitory effects of FD on both p-STAT1 and *IL33* mRNA expression were
335 maintained when FD was removed by washing the cells before addition of IFN- γ . We showed that p-
336 STAT1 levels were not reduced when cells were first pretreated with FD, followed by stimulation with
337 IFN- γ in absence of FD, whereas *IL33* mRNA expression was still repressed, although to a lesser extent

338 (Figure 3C-D). Altogether, this suggests that FD reduces expression of IL-33 at least in part by
339 interfering with IFN- γ -interferon-gamma receptor (IFNGR)-JAK-STAT1 signaling in IFN- γ -stimulated S-
340 PBEC (Figure 3F).

341

342 **Effects of farm dust *TSLP* mRNA and on expression of other proinflammatory mediators**

343 In addition to its effects on IL-33, we next investigated if FD also affected the expression of another
344 epithelial alarmin such as TSLP. To this end, S-PBEC were pre-treated with FD and next stimulated with
345 IL-4/Poly(I:C), which is known to induce TSLP²². FD decreased the expression of *TSLP* in S-PBEC, both
346 at baseline and after IL-4/Poly(I:C)- stimulation (Figure 4A).

347 Since we have previously reported that part of the effects of FD on PBEC can be explained by the
348 presence of putative TLR2 ligands in FD²⁹, we therefore first investigated if treatment with the
349 TLR2/TLR1 ligand Pam3CSK has similar effects on *IL33* mRNA expression as FD. In contrast to FD, we
350 found that Pam3CSK had no effect on *IL33* mRNA expression in TNF- α /IFN- γ -exposed S-PBEC (Figure
351 S5). We next investigated if FD treatment also affects expression and release of the proinflammatory
352 chemokine IL-8 (*CXCL8*), which is known to be increased after TLR2-activation³⁹. To this end, S-PBEC
353 were pre-treated with FD and next stimulated with both TNF- α /IFN- γ and IL-4/Poly(I:C). We found that
354 *CXCL8* mRNA expression was indeed increased by FD after 6 h alone and was further increased in
355 presence of TNF- α /IFN- γ (effect of FD not significant) or IL-4/Poly(I:C) respectively (Figure 4B). Effects
356 of FD on *CXCL8* mRNA was further confirmed at the protein level after 6 h showing a trend towards
357 significance after FD treatment on IL-8 release at baseline and after stimulation with TNF- α /IFN- γ
358 (Figure S6). At 24 h, IL-8 release was further increased by both TNF- α /IFN- γ and IL-4/Poly(I:C) and this
359 effect was inhibited by FD (Figure S6). Since our experiments suggest that the effects of FD might be
360 linked to inhibition of INF- γ -INFR-signaling, we further explored the effects of FD on other interferon-
361 stimulated genes, i.e. *CXCL10*, *IRF1* and *ICAM1*^{40,41}. We found that FD indeed repressed expression of
362 *CXCL10*, *IRF1*, and *ICAM1*, which was elevated after exposure to both TNF- α /IFN- γ and IL-4/Poly(I:C)

363 or by TNF- α /IFN- γ alone (*ICAM1*) respectively (Figure 4B-E). This indicates that FD alone might induce
364 an initial marginal proinflammatory response in bronchial epithelial cells by increasing IL-8 expression
365 and release, and subsequently may dampen the effect of proinflammatory stimuli at a later stage,
366 possibly through interference with interferon signaling.

367

368 **Discussion**

369 In this study, we showed that FD reduces the expression of the alarmin IL-33 in primary bronchial
370 epithelial cell cultures following RV infection or exposure to the proinflammatory cytokines TNF-
371 α /IFN- γ . This finding illustrated another protective mechanism of FD, which may help to explain why
372 FD-exposure protects against wheezing, allergies, and asthma in young children. When exploring the
373 mechanisms underlying this inhibitory effect of FD, we observed that FD acts on IFN- γ induced STAT1
374 phosphorylation, which is part of the IFN- γ -IFNGR downstream signaling pathway regulating IL-33
375 expression. We additionally showed that FD inhibited the induction of other alarmins and
376 proinflammatory mediators.

377 Our findings demonstrating the inhibitory effect of FD on IL-33 expression are in line with two previous
378 murine studies studying the role of bacteria or bacteria-derived components: one study showed that
379 LPS treatment reduced expression of HDM-induced IL-33 expression in murine lung epithelial cells²⁸,
380 while in another mouse model, the standardized lysate of airway bacteria OM-85, was also able to
381 inhibit early *Alternaria*-induced IL-33 secretion in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) and subsequent ILC2
382 recruitment to the lung⁴². These observations were in contrast to a study in neonatal mice that were
383 treated with *A. iwoffii* (a bacterium found in cattle farms⁴³), which showed that HDM-induced IL-33
384 levels were not inhibited by the bacterial isolate⁴⁴. Furthermore, our observation that IL-33 was
385 predominantly localized in the nucleus of basal cells of differentiated ALI-PBEC cultures is in line with
386 *in vivo* observations, showing that IL-33 expression was localized to a subset of KRT5⁺, KRT14⁺, and
387 TRP63⁺ basal cells in bronchial tissue derived from COPD patients⁴⁵. There are some major differences

388 between S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC cultures, which might help to explain why the observed effects of FD
389 were more pronounced in S-PBEC compared to ALI-PBEC: Cultures of S-PBEC consists of a monolayer
390 of solely TP63⁺ basal cells, which are the IL-33-expressing- and thus target cells for FD, and secondly
391 these cells are flat (rendering a larger surface area) and have weaker cell-cell interactions compared
392 to the pseudostratified ALI-PBEC cultures, which only consist out of 31% basal cells⁴⁶, making S-PBEC
393 more accessible and responsive to FD.

394 To unravel the mechanisms underlying the FD-mediated inhibition of IFN- γ -induced IL-33 expression,
395 we show that treatment with FD inhibits STAT1 phosphorylation, which is part of the IFN- γ -IFNGR
396 downstream signalling that regulates expression of *IL33*. We furthermore demonstrated that, in
397 addition to *IL33*, also expression of other IFN- γ -inducible genes such as *CXCL10*, *IRF1* and *ICAM1* was
398 inhibited by FD. This effect on STAT1 phosphorylation was not observed when cells were only pre-
399 treated with FD prior to IFN- γ stimulation in absence of FD, suggesting that FD “physically” interferes
400 with IFN- γ -mediated activation of the IFNGR and/or downstream IFN- γ -signalling. Although the
401 inhibitory effects of FD on IFN- γ -induced p-STAT1 were absent upon removal by washing, the
402 inhibitory effect of solely a pre-treatment with FD on expression of *IL33* still persisted, suggesting that
403 FD affects other (yet unknown) signalling pathways as well. Interestingly, FD also inhibited IL-
404 4/Poly(I:C)-mediated TSLP expression, even though this expression is independent of IFN signalling²².
405 This suggests that FD may also have an inhibitory effect on TLR3-, NF- κ B-, and/or IRF-3 signalling
406 pathways, which are known to be involved in Poly(I:C)-mediated expression of *TSLP*²².

407 FD is a mix of several active compounds, including but not limited to microbial-derived molecules such
408 as endotoxins and TLR2 ligands^{29,47}, animal-derived- and plant-derived molecules^{47,48}. Since airway
409 epithelial cells have low expression of the myeloid differentiation protein-2 (MD-2) coreceptor for
410 TLR4⁴⁹, human airway epithelial cells are less responsive to endotoxins compared to immune cells and
411 mouse airway epithelial cells. For that reason, we have excluded the possibility that the effect of FD
412 on IL-33 expression is dependent on TLR4. In previous studies, we included the TLR2/TLR1 ligand
413 Pam3CSK as a positive control based on its similar activities to FD on both epithelial barrier function²⁹.

414 We therefore did investigate if the FD-mediated effects on IL-33 expression could be indeed TLR2-
415 dependent and found that Pam3CSK had no effect on *IL33* mRNA expression. We may therefore
416 reason that it is unlikely that the observed inhibitory effects of FD on the expression of epithelial
417 alarmins are due to TLR4 or TLR2/1 ligands.

418 One of the strengths of this study is that we used both undifferentiated and fully differentiated
419 primary airway epithelial cells that were obtained from multiple donors, instead of tumor-derived or
420 immortalized airway epithelial cell lines, thereby increasing the relevance of our findings. It needs to
421 be noted that PBEC used in this study were not derived from healthy donors, but from tumor-free
422 bronchial tissue derived from patients who often have smoked and underwent lung resection surgery
423 for lung cancer. This study also has a few limitations. We were not able to show whether active release
424 of IL-33 was also inhibited by FD-treatment, when using papain as an activator of IL-33 release in S-
425 PBEC. As mentioned above, FD is a mix of several active compounds. Identifying the active component
426 in FD that is responsible for inhibiting IL-33 expression is worth pursuing, but here beyond the scope
427 of the study, which is more focused on the effects and mechanism of action of FD on the airway
428 epithelium.

429 Our findings may have implications for understanding of mechanisms underlying the protective effects
430 of a farming environment on allergy and asthma development in children. By limiting the release of
431 epithelial alarmins through exposure to FD, the activation of immune cells and subsequent production
432 of Th2 cytokines could be reduced. This may alleviate wheezing symptoms and decrease epithelial
433 damage and remodeling. Additional studies are needed to confirm whether children growing up on
434 traditional farms have indeed lower airway levels of IL-33 after viral infection or exposure to allergens.
435 Additionally, future research should aim to identify the active component(s) responsible for these
436 protective effects.

437 In conclusion, our study demonstrates that FD suppresses the induction of IL-33 in human bronchial
438 epithelial cells during RV infection and exposure to proinflammatory cytokines *in vitro*. This may partly

439 be achieved *via* the inhibition of IFN- γ -induced STAT1 phosphorylation. We furthermore
440 demonstrated that FD additionally suppresses the induction of other alarmins and proinflammatory
441 mediators, which might implicate a broad dampening effect of FD on inflammation, for example after
442 viral-airway infections. These findings provide insight into the putative protective role of FD against
443 allergy and asthma development in children living on a farm.

444

445

446 **Statement of use of human patient resection material**

447 Cells were isolated from macroscopically normal lung tissue obtained from patients undergoing
448 resection surgery for lung cancer at the Leiden University Medical Center, the Netherlands. Patients
449 from which this lung tissue was derived were enrolled in the biobank via a no-objection system for
450 coded anonymous further use of such tissue (www.coreon.org). However, since 01-09-2022, patients
451 are enrolled in the biobank using active informed consent in accordance with local regulations from
452 the LUMC biobank with approval by the institutional medical ethical committee (B20.042/Ab/ab and
453 B20.042/Kb/kb).

454

455 **Conflict of interest**

456 JS, MT and DN declare no conflicts of interest related to this work. CM is inventor of the following
457 patents: PCT application number EP21189353, entitled “Proteins identified from barn dust extract for
458 the prevention and treatment of diseases” and PCT application, serial number PCT/EP2019/085016,
459 entitled “Barn Dust Extract for the Prevention and Treatment of Diseases”. BR is inventor in PCT
460 application number EP21189353, entitled “Proteins identified from barn dust extract for the
461 prevention and treatment of diseases”. EM report a grant form Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Award 2013
462 of the German Research Foundation. EM is inventor of the following patents: EP2361632 (“Specific
463 environmental bacteria for the protection from and/or the treatment of allergic, chronic inflammatory
464 and/or autoimmune disorders”), EP1411977 (“Composition containing bacterial antigens used for the
465 prophylaxis and the treatment of allergic diseases”), EP1637147 (“Stable dust extract for allergy
466 Protection”), PCT/US2021/016918, entitled “Therapeutic Fractions and Proteins from Asthma-
467 Protective Farm Dust”, PCT application number EP21189353, entitled “Proteins identified from barn
468 dust extract for the prevention and treatment of diseases”, in PCT application, serial number
469 PCT/EP2019/085016, entitled “Barn Dust Extract for the Prevention and Treatment of Diseases”. EM
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483

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621 **Figure 1. Effects of farm dust extract (FD) on IL-33 mRNA and protein expression in undifferentiated**
 622 **and fully differentiated primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC).** S-PBEC (n = 4-5
 623 donor mixes; 4-5 different donors/mix) and ALI-PBEC (n = 5 donor mixes; 4-5 different donors/mix)
 624 were first preincubated with 200 µg/mL (S-PBEC) or with 400 µg/mL (ALI-PBEC) farm dust extract (FD)
 625 for 24 h (A). To assess effects of FD on rhinovirus (RV)-induced *IL33* expression: FD was removed, and
 626 cells were subsequently infected with mock or with 0.5 MOI RV-A1B for 48 h (B-C). Assessment of
 627 effects of FD on cytokine-induced IL-33 expression: both S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC were stimulated with
 628 20 ng/mL TNF-α/30 ng/mL IFN-γ in presence or absence of FD for 6 h to assess *IL33* gene expression

629 (D, F) and for 8 h to assess IL-33 intracellular protein expression by using HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter
630 cells, and by confocal immunofluorescence staining (E, G-I). (B-D, F) Expression of *IL33* mRNA was
631 determined by qPCR. Normalized gene expression was calculated by using the expression of tyrosine
632 3-monooxygenase/tryptophan 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta (*YWHAZ*) and ribosomal
633 protein L27 (*RPL27*) as reference genes. Next, fold changes in gene expression compared to CNTRL
634 were calculated and data are shown as individual values, and as means ± SEM. (E,G) Intracellular IL-33
635 protein levels in the supernatant of the freeze-thaw-damaged cells were measured by using HEK-
636 Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells, which were seeded in a 96-well plate and incubated with the conditioned
637 medium of the stimulated S-PBEC for 24 h. IL-33 induced SEAP levels in the HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter
638 cell supernatant were measured using a spectrophotometer at O.D. 650 nm. (H-I) Confocal
639 immunofluorescence staining of IL-33 in S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC (n = 3 donor mixes; 4-5 donors/mix),
640 DAPI (blue) was used to stain the nuclei with and an antibody detecting IL-33 (green). The images were
641 further analyzed using maximum intensity view. To quantify the number of IL-33⁺ cells, IL-33⁺ and
642 DAPI⁺ nuclei were counted per 62.500 μm² field. Per donor mix, three fields were analyzed. Data are
643 presented as individual values, including means ± SEM and were tested for significance using a
644 Student's paired t-test or the two-way ANOVA and the Šídák or Dunnett's post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, **
645 p < 0.01.

646

647

648 **Figure 2. Co-localization of IL-33 with basal cells in undifferentiated and fully differentiated primary**
 649 **bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC and ALI-PBEC).** Confocal immunofluorescence staining of IL-33
 650 (green) in combination with epithelial cell makers of ciliated- (Foxj1; pink), goblet (Muc5AC; red),
 651 secretory (goblet and club cells; red)- and basal cells (TP63; red) in S-PBEC (IL-33 and TP63 only) and
 652 ALI-PBEC (of 1 donor mix; confirmed in 2 other donor mixes [4-5 donors/mix]). DAPI (blue) was used
 653 to stain the nuclei and antibodies (table II) were used for detection of epithelial cell markers
 654 respectively.

655

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656 **Figure 3. Effect of FD on IFN- γ -downstream pathways in submerged cultures of primary bronchial**

657 **epithelial cells (S-PBEC). S-PBEC (n = 4 donor mixes; 4-5 different donors/mix) were first preincubated**

658 **with inhibitors of downstream IFN- γ -signaling pathways (JAK, p38 MAPK, EGFR and NF- κ B) or with 200**

659 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ farm dust extract (FD) and subsequently stimulated with 30 ng/mL IFN- γ for 30 min to assess
660 phosphorylated (p)-STAT1, p-p38 and p-EGFR by western blot analysis, or for 6 h to determine *IL33*
661 mRNA expression (A-B). To investigate the effect of only pretreatment of FD on IFN- γ -mediated p-
662 STAT1 expression and on subsequent *IL33* mRNA expression, S-PBEC (n = 3 donor mixes; 4-5
663 donors/mix) were pretreated with FD or CNTRL in BD starvation for 24 h, followed by 1 h preincubation
664 with fresh FD, or removal of FD by washing the cells three times with BD starvation. IFN- γ was added
665 1 h after the final washing step for 30 min to measure p-STAT1 by western blot analysis and for 6 h to
666 assess *IL33* mRNA expression by qPCR (C-D). (A, D) Normalized expression of *IL33* mRNA was
667 determined by qPCR and calculated by using the expression of tyrosine 3-monooxygenase/tryptophan
668 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta (*YWHAZ*) and ribosomal protein L27 (*RPL27*) as reference
669 genes. Data are presented as individual values, including means \pm SEM. (B-C) SDS-PAGE gel
670 electrophoresis followed by western blot analysis, was used to detect p-STAT1, p-p38 and p-EGFR in
671 cell lysates. LL-37 stimulation was used as positive control for activation of STAT1, MAPK p38 and EGFR
672 signaling. To assess effects of the inhibitors and of FD on p-STAT1, p-p38 and p-EGFR, densitometry
673 was used and the ratios between p-STAT1 and the reference protein GAPDH was calculated for each
674 sample. (F) Proposed mechanism underlying the inhibitory effects of FD on INF- γ -induced *IL33*
675 expression. Data are presented as fold change (compared to control stimulated S-PBEC) \pm SEM. Data
676 were analyzed using a two-way ANOVA and Dunnett's post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p <
677 0.001, **** p < 0.001.

Figure 4

A

B

C

D

E

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679 **Figure 4. Effect of FD on *TSLP*, *IL8* and *CXCL10* mRNA expression in cultures of primary bronchial**

680 **epithelial cells (S-PBEC).** S-PBEC (n = 5 different donors) were first preincubated with 200 μ g/mL (S-

681 PBEC) or with 400 μ g/mL (ALI-PBEC) farm dust extract (FD) for 24 h and subsequently stimulated with

682 20 ng/mL TNF- α /30 ng/mL IFN- γ or with 50 ng/mL IL-4/5 μ g/mL Poly(I:C) in presence or absence of FD

683 for 6 h to assess mRNA expression of *TSLP*, *IL8*, *CXCL10*, *IRF1* and *ICAM1*. For statistical analysis of

684 genes with large effects of the stimuli on gene expression levels (> 100-fold change) such as *CXCL10*

685 and *ICAM1*, the fold changes in gene expression levels were log-transformed to obtain a normal

686 distribution of the data. Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Data were analyzed using a two-way

687 ANOVA and Dunnett's post-hoc test. * p < 0.05 p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

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